

A new record of *Soosia diodonta* (Férussac, 1821) (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Helicodontidae) in Bulgaria

DILIAN GEORGIEV¹ & SLAVEYA STOYCHEVA²

¹Department of Ecology and Environmental Conservation, University of Plovdiv, Tzar Assen Str. 24, BG-4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: diliangeorgiev@abv.bg

²NGO Green Balkans, Shesti Septemvri Str. 160, BG-4000, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: slaveyastoycheva@abv.bg

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The second finding of the rare south-east European endemic land snail *Soosia diodonta* (Férussac, 1821) in Bulgaria was reported. The locality was situated in Eastern Stara Planina Mts., west from Kotel town, near the road to Zeleniche Forestry and the Kotlenska River, before Prikazna Cave, UTM: MH 55. *Soosia diodonta* was found in beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) forest on a limestone terrain near a river. It was the most eastern ever known locality of this species.

Key words: *Soosia diodonta*, new locality, Bulgaria

Introduction

The land snail species *Soosia diodonta* (Férussac, 1821) (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Helicodontidae) is a south-east European endemic species which occurs in the Eastern Serbia, Western Romania and Bulgaria (DAMJANOV & LIKHAREV 1975). The only known locality of this species in Bulgaria was near the Boyanski waterfall in Vitosha Mts. (URBAŃSKI 1964), but its occurrence in the country remained uncertain (DEDOV 1998).

Material and methods

Two trips in Eastern Stara Planina Mts. for gathering malacological materials were made in June 2003 and September 2007. The material was collected by hand and using a sieve for the soil samples (DAMJANOV & LIKHAREV 1975). The land snail species names used in the paper are after HUBENOV (2005).

Results

Locality of *Soosia diodonta*: Eastern Stara Planina Mts., west from Kotel Town, near the road to Zeleniche Forestry and the Kotlenska River, before Prikazna Cave, UTM: MH 55, 42°53' N, 26°24' E, 600 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1). This locality is the most eastern known one for this species.

Material: (1) Jun 2003 (the exact date not known) – two live individuals, under a dead tree trunk, these specimens were not killed and were released back in the nature; (2) 13 Sep 2007 – one shell in a *Fagus sylvatica* tree leaf detritus, dimensions: shell height 4.8 mm, shell width 10.9 mm (Fig. 2). The shell collected on 13 Sep 2007 was deposited in the collection of the first author.

Habitat: A beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) forest on a limestone terrain near a river.

For other land malacofauna in the same UTM-grid square see Table 1.

Fig. 1. The new locality of finding the *Soosia diodonta* (Férussac, 1821) in Bulgaria.

Fig. 2. Shell of the specimen of *Soosia diodonta* (Férussac, 1821) found on 13 Sep 2007.

Table 1. Land malacofauna of the UTM locality of finding of *Soosia diodonta* (Ferussac, 1821). Remark: The species *O. glaber* was also found living in the caves (Drianovskata Peshtera Cave).

species	habitat		
	<i>Farus sylvatica</i> forest	<i>Carpinus orientalis</i> forest	Grassland
<i>Pomatias rivulare</i> (Eichwald, 1829)	*	*	*
<i>Carychium tridentatum</i> (Risso, 1826)	*		
<i>Chondrina avenacea</i> (Bruguiere, 1729)	*		
<i>Merdigera obscura</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	*		
<i>Zebrina detrita</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)		*	*
<i>Cochlodina laminata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	*		
<i>Macedonica marginata</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	*		
<i>Mentissela rebeli</i> (Sturany, 1897)	*		
<i>Laciniaria plicata</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	*		
<i>Balea biplicata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	*		
<i>Arion silvaticus</i> Lohmander, 1937	*		*
<i>Euconulus fulvus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	*		
<i>Vitrea diaphana</i> (Studer, 1820)	*		
<i>Aegopinella pura</i> (Alder, 1830)	*		
<i>Aegopinella minor</i> (Stabile, 1864)	*		
<i>Oxychilus investigatus</i> Riedel, 1993	*		*
<i>Oxychilus glaber</i> (Rossmässler, 1835)	*		
<i>Oxychilus inopinatus</i> (Uličný, 1887)	*		
<i>Daudebardia rufa</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	*		
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1931)			*
<i>Tandonia cristata</i> (Kaleniczenko, 1851)	*		
<i>Limax maximus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	*		
<i>Deroceras sturanyi</i> (Simroth, 1894)	*		*
<i>Helicigona trizona</i> (Rossmassler, 1835)	*	*	*
<i>Cepaea vindobonensis</i> (Ferussac, 1821)		*	*
<i>Helix lucorum</i> Linnaeus, 1757	*		
<i>Bradybaena fruticum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)			*
<i>Soosia diodonta</i> (Ferussac, 1821)	*		
<i>Linholmiola girva</i> (Friveldszcky, 1835)	*		
<i>Trichia erjavecii</i> Brusina, 1870	*		
<i>Xerolenta obvia</i> (Menke, 1828)		*	
<i>Monachoides incarnatus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	*		
<i>Monacha</i> cf. <i>carascaliodes</i> (Bourguignat, 1855)		*	
<i>Monacha</i> sp.	*		
<i>Euomphalia strigella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)			*

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